

Organising Research Data Files

Well-organised research files and documentation make it easier to find, understand, share, and reuse data. Clear organisation supports collaboration and reduces the risk of confusion, duplication of work, and accidental data loss.

Use a clear folder structure

Create a folder structure to follow throughout the project lifecycle. Keep it simple, hierarchical, and logical.

Best Practice

- Keep raw data separate from processed data.
- Remove temporary folders as soon as possible.
- Avoid excessive subfolders and nest them simply.
- Keep shared folders tidy and easy to navigate, with easy to understand names.
- Include a README file.

Create and maintain README files

A README file, saved as a TXT file, contains crucial details relating to the datasets. Assisting with how to understand and use the data from the project.

A README should include:

- The project title
- Short project description
- Description of file structure and naming conventions
- Brief description and list of files associated to the README
- Information on data collection and processing
- Contact information
- License and citation information

Best Practice

- Create a README for related clusters of related files or datasets.
- Keep the README short and practical.
- Update it whenever there are changes to file structure.
- Write for someone who is not familiar with the project or topic.

Use consistent file naming conventions

Naming conventions make it easier to locate, search, and identify files. The naming convention should be meaningful, and used consistently. The simple name should clearly indicate what it is about, when it was created, and what version it is.

Examples

No	Project T may 2 2026 finalfinalversion
Yes	20260620_ProjectT_Report_Author_v05
No	raw data from 09/03/2025 V1%2 Lewis
Yes	20250903_ProjectT_RawData_Lewis_v1-2

Best Practice

- Include the following in the file name:
 - Project name (abbreviated if needed)
 - Author (whole name or initials)
 - Date (YYYYMMDD format)
 - Content description (abbreviated if needed)
 - Version number (v01, v1-2, v01-3)
- Do NOT use special characters (#\$,%, etc)
- Increase the version number after updates.
- Archive older versions of files instead of overwriting them.

Common mistakes to avoid

- Mixing raw and processed data in the same folder
 - Can lead to confusion of what data is being used
- Saving files in many different locations or on personal drives
 - Can lead to important information being lost
- Keeping multiple files called “final”
 - Can result in incorrect items being published or presented
- Using different naming styles in the same project
 - Can lead to data being lost and general confusion

Quick check

- Is the folder structure clear and hierarchical?
- Are raw and processed datasets stored in separate files?
- Is there a README?
- Are file names consistent and clear?
- Is versioning being used?
- Could a new team member understand the files quickly?